

EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS FOR JOB SEEKERS

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ABSTRACT:

A job seeker needs to possess a number of skills for being employed in reputed companies. In the present scenario he has to be a good communicator of ideas and concepts in the communicative language, English. Reasoning Abilities, Verbal Aptitude Communicative Competency, Numerical Ability etc. enable the prospective candidates get better employment opportunities. Training the outstanding students to deliver impromptu talks, short speeches, and taking part in Dialogues and Group Discussions will equip them with confidence to face the interviews. Personality traits are well-formed with the development of Life Skills and Soft Skills. Job aspirants have to develop problem-solving abilities, critical and creative thinking to find out solutions in critical situations. Interpersonal relationships are to be established and candidates should be acquainted with the four major skills of language viz. Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. Listening to the speeches of eminent literateurs and talks by industry professionals will create awareness as to what is required of them. While at college or university the candidates should utilize the opportunities to acquire the relevant skills, in addition to achieving Academic Excellence to be placed in lucrative positions.

KEYWORDS: Communications, Job, Placement Proficiency, Skills

EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS FOR JOB SEEKERS:

A job seeking candidate requires a number of skills for getting employed with a decent salary in a lucrative position in any reputed firm. Primarily he has to be an efficient communicator--- a communicator of ideas, concepts and the functioning of a system. Whatever be his academic credentials, unless he demonstrates his skills in a common language, he may not be a success in his career. For a successful candidate it becomes obligatory on his part to be proficient in the communicative language.

Communication skills are a must for all, let them be professionals, teachers or students. Emphasis is to be laid on developing the speaking skills among all. Competency in English is the need of the hour for job aspirants and they ought to have learnt the use of simple and correct English. Acquiring Communication skills

through different language acquisition devices, practising the acquired skills continuously for the flow of ideas and executing them in the proper way are prerequisites for job seekers.

Developing communicative ability is an integral part of Soft Skills development. Excelling in the Verbal Aptitude, enriching Reasoning Abilities at the stage of graduation will enable the prospective candidates to have their skills honed for better employment opportunities. Outstanding students could be indulged in activities like giving impromptu talks, delivering extempore and prepared speeches, assuming Role Play, taking part in Dialogues, and participating in Group Discussions, developing conversational skills, organizing ideas in a coherent way and utilizing them in the paper presentation sessions in seminars and symposia, selecting and presenting a good topic in the thrust area, actively participating in Debates and expressing concepts, ideas in a convincing way are of streamlining factors towards the projection of one's personality at the interviews. Personality traits are to be well-formed with the nurturing of Life Skills for better placement prospects.

Aspirants of jobs are to develop problem-solving abilities by carefully analyzing the situations and finding suitable solutions to problems when they crop up. They should also sharpen their critical and creative thinking, establish inter-personal relationships and thereby promote leadership qualities. The writing tasks will have to be presented in simple, easy steps in unambiguous statements utilizing rich, relevant technical vocabulary. Apart from written communication in the field of oral communication steps should be employed to develop speaking skills. Expressing ideas in clear cut terms in faultless English will be an added advantage to job seekers.

All learners are to be conversant with the four major skills of language learning, viz. LSRW. Listening to the speeches of eminent masters of life and literature and talks by the industry professionals, keenly observing panel discussions, reading the brochures of business institutes and pursuing the manuscripts, documents related to the firms provide the candidates with the essential information for placements. Reading standard newspapers like 'The Hindu', 'The Indian Express' and 'The Deccan Herald' will be of immense value to the Readers in improving their Reading Skills.

In addition to Listening, in classes also special emphasis is to be laid especially on promoting Speaking skills in English. Exercises in Writing Skills are to be administered in such a way that they are complacent with the task of writing. Some may have the problem of writing a good hand and such can be given practice in the art of handwriting---using appropriate strokes, curves, pauses, spacing, punctuation marks etc.

Learners at universities and colleges have to be motivated intellectually and they are to be acquainted with Soft Skills like Verbal Aptitude, Numerical Ability and Test of Reasoning, so that they perform well and fulfil the requirements of companies at the time of recruitment. While at college or university undergoing the Soft Skills Training light up the prospects of employment for students.

A person's Soft Skills EQ (Emotional Intelligence Quotient) in an essential factor contributing to the success of a firm. The Workforce Profile has defined 60 "Soft Skills" increasingly sought out by employers. Only a strong emotional foundation with academic excellence can lead to success in one's career. One should develop good Soft Skills which include self- management, social graces, communication skills, personality skills, behavioral skills and people skills for managing people easily and effectively. The traits most expected of the candidates are "Positive work ethic", "Good attitude" and "Desire to learn and be trained".

After evaluating the technical and conceptual skills of a candidate, an organization looks for the team-building and team-participating activity of the individual. Group Discussion is an area or to be precise a methodology adopted by the company to select the right candidate for it. This is where many students falter in their performance and fail to qualify themselves for placement. The following aspects are generally observed and understood to have formed part of Group Discussion.

- Verbal communication
- Non-verbal communication
- Decision making ability
- Co-operation

As a member of a company, after recruitment, one has to be a part of a team and interact with other members. At the end of the discussion, some of the following personality traits will be analyzed by an expert of the company. A candidate's 'initiative' to take part actively in discussions, his 'analytical skills', his 'ability to think differently', the "creativity he possesses and his 'flexible nature' will all be judged. The motivational skills, the team-building ability, the relationships he establishes with others will be brought to lime light in the Group Discussion sessions. Candidates placed in

higher positions are expected to bring in best results by interacting with team members. There is also scope for enriching team spirit through Group Discussions.

How good the candidates in their communicative ability are can also be assessed by Group Discussion method. Job seekers have the opportunity to exhibit their speaking skills. An aspirant is required to be not merely sound in intelligence but to be emotionally stable as well. The candidates placed are expected to be open- minded and tolerant of the opinions of his subordinates so as to function effectively and produce desired outcomes. They should have the inclination to shoulder the responsibilities of the posts they hold. They are to fulfil, as is expected of them, the objectives of the concern and meet the targets in production, marketing and sales.

Academic achievements, Soft Skills and Life Skills go a long way in getting suitable placements for graduates. A prospective candidate acquires the ability instantaneously to get placed. Communicative Competency, Problem-Solving Ability, Emotional Intelligence Quotient, Leadership Qualities, Inter-personal Relationships and rigorous training in Soft Skills act as helping factors for job seekers in entering into better employment services.

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